

Beyond DTI: Higher Order Models in Cardiac dMRI

Justino R. Rodríguez-Galván, Susana Merino-Caviedes, Antonio Tristán-Vega,
Carlos Alberola-López

1. Introduction

Diffusion MRI (dMRI) is a kind of clinical imaging focused on measuring Brownian movement of water within body tissues. Although high resolution dMRI is widely implemented in neurology, there are some peculiarities of the cardiological counterpart that hinder its implementation. As myocardium has peculiar T_2 and T_E parameters, doubts have been raised on the usefulness of Higher Order (HO) models [1]. However, recent structural models of the heart [2] affirm that there are some little membranes called “sheetlets” responsible of the thickening of the myocardium walls during beating movement, which Diffusion Tensor Imaging (DTI) is unable to detect. The aim of this work is to check whether HO models can make a difference over DTI and how apart both approaches are.

2. Materials and methods

For this study, two ex-vivo pig hearts acquisitions with the same sampling scheme of 216 gradients at 6 shells at b-values 300, 600, 900, 1200, 2000 and 3600 s/mm² were processed.

Methodology consisted of computing both DTI and an HO model, in particular, General Cross Validation pixelwise HYDI-DSI (Hybrid Diffusion Imaging) [3]. For either of these models, Ensemble Average Propagator (EAP) was computed leaving apart 3 gradients per shell (q_{test}) and then, $E(q_{test})$ was reconstructed with that non-fully-sampled EAP. This process was carried out in a 10-fold cross validation approach. Reconstructions of each fold were grouped by shell and then, empirical Non-Gaussianity (NG) was computed.

$$NG = \frac{E\{[E(q_{test}) - E_{DTI}(q_{test})]^2\} - E\{[E(q_{test}) - E_{DSI}(q_{test})]^2\}}{E\{E(q_{test})^2\}}$$

3. Results

Figure 1 depicts NG in myocardium for all volumes.

Figure 1: NG for 3 different slices (horizontal axis) for every b -value (vertical axis).

4. Discussion & conclusion

As it has been shown, NG is predominantly bigger than zero in the myocardium, getting bigger as we move further from the center. These facts confirm the usefulness of these models, enabling the further exploration in this area of research. A comparison with other well-known models like MAPL [4] and an analytical implementation of NG is programmed for further researching.

References

- [1] Mekkaoui, C., Reese, T. G., Jackowski, M. P., Bhat, H., & Sosnovik, D. E. (2017). Diffusion MRI in the heart. *NMR in Biomedicine*, 30(3), e3426.
- [2] Nielles-Vallespin, S., Scott, A., Ferreira, P., Khaliq, Z., Pennell, D., & Firmin, D. (2020). Cardiac Diffusion: Technique and Practical App. *Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging*, 52(2), 348-368
- [3] Tristán-Vega A, Pieciak T, París G, Rodríguez-Galván JR, Aja-Fernández S. HYDI-DSI revisited: constrained non-parametric EAP imaging without q-space re-gridding. *Medical Image Analysis* 2022.
- [4] Fick, R. H., Wassermann, D., Caruyer, E., & Deriche, R. (2016). MAPL: Tissue microstructure estimation using Laplacian-regularized MAP-MRI and its application to HCP data. *NeuroImage*, 134, 365-385.